

SOCIO-CULTURAL BEHAVIOR OF GRADE 10 PUBLIC JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SDO URDANETA CITY

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Socio-Cultural Behavior of Grade 10 Public Junior High School Students in SDO Urdaneta City

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Abstract

The study delved on socio-cultural behavior of Grade 10 students in SDO Urdaneta City. The study determined the profile of the respondents, the extent of manifestations of socio-cultural behaviors, the significant relationship between the extent of manifestation of the respondent's socio-cultural behaviors across profile variables, and the intervention activities that could be proposed to enhance their socio-cultural behavior. The descriptive method of research was used in this study. Findings showed that majority of the Grade 10 students are 16 years old, male, having a very satisfactory performance, with married parents working as farmers and low income earners. In addition, the Grade 10 students possess strong manifestation of their socio-cultural behaviors. Further, academic performance and teacher-related behaviors are correlated. Hence, a proposed list of activities was crafted based on the salient findings of the study to enhance the socio-cultural behaviors of the students.

Keywords: *socio-cultural behavior, family-related behaviors, individual-related behaviors, peer-related behaviors, teacher-related behaviors*

Introduction

Every society has a set of values, beliefs, traditions, and habits known as their socio-cultural values. These values shape how we approach risk, how we view careers, our perceptions of money, and our ideas of an ideal lifestyle. Because of this, socio-cultural values are one of many interacting factors that can impact educational development within a country.

The high school students are now confronted with many challenges in their lives most specifically in their socio-cultural behavior as a result of the rapid technological changes. Basically, man's socio-cultural behaviors depend on their relationships with others and the cultural orientations of their own. It is therefore inevitable that the students have associated with diverse beliefs, attitudes, ideas, moral and spiritual values which have great influence on their socio-cultural behavior. The students may help and strengthen one another, improving in disposition, in knowledge or by permitting themselves to become careless and unfaithful. They may exert an influence that is demoralizing. High school students in these present times are observed to be careless in choosing their associates with questionable morals, of bad principles which have influenced their whole being.

Furthermore, students identify with certain groups to experience a feeling of belonging. Many students at different ages have a strong need to belong to groups, because groups provide a source of motivation, belongingness, and acceptance. They may be identified with certain groups due to social class, race or religion. These categories might be some of the social constructions of cultures that provide a sense of cultural identity. The different sets of beliefs that individuals hold about themselves is termed self-concept or self-image (Bennet, 2013).

Socio-cultural factors are larger scale forces within societies and culture that have an impact on the thoughts, feelings, and behaviors of the individual members of those societies and cultures. Many people consider that learning has to do with the processes within learner but culture in which any person learns sets agenda for the learning in numerous ways. It determines what is learned and it also influences that when and how it is learned. What, when and how an individual learns is influenced in many ways by culture in which learning occurs and social interaction processes in which learner involves. It is the quality of all these collaborations and interactions rather than the processes solely within a learner that determines the quality of learning.

Recent evidence from the study of Harris (2016), suggests that the complex web of social relationship, students experience with peers, adults in the school and family members exerts a much greater influence on their behavior. This process starts with family relationships or primary caregivers in their lives which form a personality either secured or unsecured.

According to Blair et.al, (2018), once students are in school, the dual factors of socialization and social status has a strong contribution in shaping their behavior. The schools process of socialization typically pressures students to be like their peers or risk social rejection and the quest for high social status drives the students to differentiate themselves in some areas.

Formal education involves the students learning based on culturally valued ideas. Both culture and the groups within culture have bodies of knowledge that they trust and believe, these factors will assist the individuals to transact in social activities. Students are the future leaders of the nation. As the world is progressing with globalization, the surrounding and personal communication play a major role in the student's life. This personal communication is based on the family side, with whom students spend most of their time.

From Wahla and Awan (2014), revealed that mobile phones usage during study and work brings negative effects on the outcome and results. In like manner, Briner (2019) said that teachers or more experienced peers were able to provide learners with the support to students that were found to evolving the understanding of their knowledge domains and development of their complex skills. Socio-

cultural factors exercise their effect within the family structure. Examples of these are attitudes, belief and the value system, and the language use at their homes etc. (Gonzalez, 2016). According to Theory of Educational Productivity presented by Walberg (1981): there are three groups of nine factors based on cognitive, affective, and behavioral skills for optimization of learning that have a great impact on the quality.

Cultures and social groups are also characterized by particular ways of thinking. For effective participation in social activities in the culture, members of the culture are expected to learn these. Some theories of learning and thinking propose that individuals learn ways of thinking directly in their social interactions with others, particularly when they are engaged in solving socially defined problems. They internalize this activity and later use the newly learned mental processes by themselves, without the support of others; cognitive development is "the conversion of social relations into mental functions" (Vygotsky, 1981, p. 165).

Rogers (2002) stated that students' deficiency of preparation for exams deals with socio-cultural factors rather than a deficiency of academic potential. Also, Gonzalez (2001) stated that socio-cultural factors have an effect within a family structure in which a type of mediation of children's and parents' behavior is found. Children and parents must develop some socio-cultural strategies to be adapted to the school system. Lori and Al-Ansari (2001) revealed that socio-cultural factors affect student's language proficiency and language learning. Normand's (2008) findings revealed that learners from very high socio-cultural families had a higher rate of progress as compared to learners from low socio-cultural family status. The low socio-economic status level of parents has a negative relationship with students' academic achievements because students with low socio-economic status have limited access to resources and sources of learning (Duke, 2000). The home environment of students also affects their academic performance. The schoolteachers can provide guidance and counseling of parents and students.

The home environment of students also affects their academic performance. The schoolteachers can provide guidance and counseling to parents of students for creating positive and better home environment for progress in learners' quality of work (Marzano, 2003). Krashen (2005) concluded that learners whose parents were educated scored higher on standardized tests than those students whose parents were not educated. Television has a significant impact on the educational process. Television influences the social behavior of students not only by teaching new behavior but also contributes to learners' views about inappropriate and appropriate behavior (Libert, 1972; Boron, 1972). The Internet provides access to vast sources of information that are hosted by various individuals and organizations worldwide on a massive network of servers (Ogungbeni, et al, 2016). Various studies have indicated that the use of the Internet by students can have a positive impact on their educational achievement (Chen & Fu & Fu, 2009).

Learners first become aware of the ways of thinking in a culture by participating with others to solve problems that they have. The actions they see being used are often referred to as 'tools'. When a problem is solved jointly with others, real-life tools may be used. Particular action sequences are linked with using these tools, for example, the act of using an axe to solve the problem of cooking, turning on a light to solve the problem of seeing in the dark, driving a car to solve the problem of needing to travel. We learn physical actions by modeling others to use them. These physical actions can be internalized as mental actions, and these become our ways of thinking.

Social groups are also characterized by ways of thinking. For effective participation in social activities in the culture, members of the culture are expected to learn these. Some theories of learning and thinking propose that individuals learn ways of thinking directly in their social interactions with others, particularly when they are engaged in solving socially defined problems. They internalize this activity and later use the newly learnt mental processes by themselves, without the support of others; cognitive development is the conversion of social relations into mental functions" (Vygotsky, 1981)

Students become aware of the ways of thinking in a culture by participating with others to solve problems that they have. The actions they see being used are often referred to as 'tools'. When a problem is solved jointly with others, real-life tools may be used. Particular action sequences are linked with using these tools, for example, the act of using an axe to solve the problem of cooking, turning on a light to solve the problem of seeing in the dark, driving a car to solve the problem of needing to travel. We learn physical actions by modeling others use them. These physical actions can be internalized as mental actions. These become their ways of thinking.

Whether or not peer group influence is an important risk factor in teenage drug abuse, there are peer groups in many communities that, in isolation from adult supervision, form more-or-less-structured disruptive and deviant groups and become involved in antisocial and illegal behavior such as vandalism, drug and alcohol use and abuse, and shoplifting. The most structured and best known of these are the urban fighting gangs of males and, increasingly, their female auxiliaries, who exhibit and value the impulsive aggression and hostility that have sometimes made us wary and even fearful of youth in our society.

Such gangs are built into the texture of their neighborhoods whose turf they often protect. When one listens to these youth, they often tell of having to distance themselves from home environments lacking even the most rudimentary family structure to support a parent-child relationship. They frequently come from single-parent homes where the mother is unable to maintain adequate behavioral controls, or if there is an adult male present, the youth is in rebellion against him, not infrequently because of seeing his mother abused or degraded. Fleeing or being pushed out into the streets, they seek out the structure and the often-severe strictures of the gang, where fidelity is to the gang and not to home or school. If neither the home nor the school provides the means of achieving an identity that allows some minimal sense of self-worth, the gang does, and usually with more excitement and immediate gratification.

While each of these risk factors can be injurious to development and destructive to social competence and an integrated and rewarding identity, the problem for those at greatest risk is that the factors are often interconnected, combining and reinforcing each other with devastating effects on the life course. Substance abuse and school failure can lead to early pregnancy for females and to lives on the fringes of employability and legitimate behavior for males. And even when we manage to reduce the risks in one area, lack of progress in another may make that success seem meaningless. Despite the fact that targeted programs have had a visible effect in reducing the incidence of dropping out among male high school students, the unemployment rate among high school graduates is one-fifth higher than the rate for high school dropouts (Wetzel, 2017.).

In a study conducted by Marquez, 2018, students who are successful in their desired career have good study habits. She commented that students should apply these good habits to all of their classes in order that their studying process will be effective.

Behavior on the other hand is a potent factor in every student's endeavor. It is rather innately acquired constructively or destructively (Cortez, 2017). Innate in this sense that man's behavior is generally endowed, acquired in the sense that man's behavior is affected by his encounters with other human beings. Thus, his behavior is influenced or changed.

The FICS Analysis encompasses the psychological, emotional, economic, cultural and social dimensions of the risk factors for dropping out affected the students/learners. A DORP plan shall be crafted by the school team after the final analysis and identification of potential dropouts.

The Department of Education (DepEd) devotes more time and resources to measure the extent of the problem. DepEd has recently launched the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) highlighting Dropout Rate as one of the focus of research in the field of education (DO No. 39, s. 2016). In addition, funds are also made available to conduct relevant research through DepEd Order No. 4, s. 2016 through the Basic Education Research Fund. As the dropout rates in the Philippines have decreased from the period, there has been a great improvement because of the lower dropout rate but still far from the goal of Philippine Education for All (EFA) 2015 National Plan of Action No. 3 on the universal school participation and total elimination of dropouts and repetition in Grades 1 to 3. Despite the increasing trend there is also an increasing disparity between the performance of boys and girls in the current educational system as indicated by the Education for All report for 2015. The cohort survival rate for girls is 9.5% greater to that of the boys. In addition, the projected population of the Philippines will soon reach 103 million; therefore, there is a need for the government to account for the increase in provision of basic services. This includes the provision of basic learning needs and skills to survive in a very competitive environment. In addition, the Department of Education has a goal to increase its key result areas, namely: access, quality and governance. In order to increase its access, schools must include in its plan a zero percent drop-out rate, 100% participation, completion and cohort survival rate which is also the DepEd's planning standard.

The FICs Profile of LARDOs and Non-LARDOs provide an insight on the characteristics of learners who are at risk and in contrast to the learners who are not considered to be at risk.

Family related factors are factors that describe their current family profile. These factors are considered important since they have huge impact on the learner's performance. Individual-related factors described the learners' current individual profile identified to have an effect on their level of engagement in school. DORP also considered as community related factors essential in determining factors that influence dropout.

Hence, it is within this premise that the researcher was motivated to conduct this study to determine the socio-cultural behaviors of students.

Research Questions

This study determined the socio-cultural behavior of Grade 10 Public Junior High School students in SDO Urdaneta City. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Junior High School student respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. academic performance;
 - 1.4. parents' civil status;
 - 1.5. monthly family income; and
 - 1.6. occupation of parents?
2. What is the extent of the manifestations of socio-cultural behaviors of the respondents along:
 - 2.1. Family-related behavior;
 - 2.2. Peer-related behavior;
 - 2.3. Community-related behavior; and
 - 2.4. Teacher-related behavior?
3. Is there significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their extent of manifestations of their socio-cultural behavior?

4. What activities can be proposed to enhance the socio-cultural behavior of the students?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive correlational research. According to Calderon and Gonzales (2013), this research design will be used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena to describe the existing situation with respect to variables or conditions in a certain situation. Since the events or conditions have already occurred or existed, relevant variables are merely selected for an analysis of their relationship. It involves hypothesis formulation, testing and will use logical methods in inductive and deductive reasoning in order to arrive at generalization.

This study used the mentioned research design descriptive in the sense that it described the student respondent's socio-cultural behavior along family relationships, peer relationships, and student-teacher relationships.

Respondents

This study involved 360 Grade 10 students who were purposively selected from schools in Urdaneta City which were considered big due to their enrolment. They came from different students from the Junior High School department of the following high schools.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

<i>Name of School</i>	<i>Total Enrolment</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>
Badipa NHS	197	60
Cabaruan NHS	123	60
Camantiles NHS	117	60
Lanampin NHS	234	60
Pedro T. Orata NHS	104	60
Palina NHS	176	60
Total		360

Instrument

The data gathering instrument used in this study included the survey questionnaire to determine the age, sex, parent's educational attainment, parent's marital status, and the monthly income of the student respondent. Their GPA is based on their grade or from SF 10 (Form 137) known as the Students Permanent Record.

There were two sets of questionnaires for this study. Part I contains the respondent's profile as to age, sex, academic performance, parent's marital status, income of the family, and occupation of parents. Part II contained questions on socio-cultural behavior along with family-related behaviors, peer-related behaviors, community-related behaviors, and teacher-related behaviors.

Procedure

As an initial move, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Urdaneta City and the different school principals of Urdaneta City to conduct the study on Socio-cultural Behavior of Grade 10 Junior High School students of SDO Urdaneta City. The researcher asked the cooperation of the teachers and section advisers of the respondents to help get the needed data. Other data were gathered through Google Forms from the respondents.

Data Analysis

Appropriate statistical treatments were employed by the researcher to come out with valid and credible interpretation of data.

To answer problem number 1 which pertains to the profile of the respondents, frequency counts and percentage were used.

To answer problem number 2 which pertains to the extent of manifestation of the socio-cultural behavior of the respondents, weighted mean was used.

To answer problem number 3 which pertains to the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their extent of manifestation of socio-cultural behaviors, Chi-Square and Point Biserial were used.

To answer problem number 4, salient findings of problem number 1, 2, and 3 served as basis in crafting proposed activities to enhance the socio-cultural behavior of students.

Results and Discussion

This section interprets, presents, and analyzes the data of the study.

Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents along with age, sex, academic performance, parents' educational attainment, parents' civil status, and monthly family income.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 2. *Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Profile Variable</i>		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Age	16	300	83%
	17	60	17%
Sex	Male	256	71%
	Female	104	29%
Academic Performance	80-84	102	28%
	85-89	213	59%
	90-95	45	13%
Parents' Civil Status	Married	321	89%
	Separated	16	4%
	Widow	17	5%
	Single Parent	6	2%
Monthly Family Income	1,000.00 - 7,999.00	45	13%
	8,000.00 - 14,999.00	181	50%
	15,000.00 - 21,999.00	96	27%
	22,000.00 - 29,000.00	25	7%
	30,000.00 and above	13	4%
Occupation of Parents	Farmer	140	39%
	Fruit/Veg. Vendor	37	10%
	Tricycle driver	125	35%
	Businessman	20	6%
	Gov't Employee (Municipal)	12	3%
	OFW	13	4%
	Teacher	13	4%

Age. It can be noted in Table 2 that 300 or 80% of the respondents are 16 years old. This implies that majority of the respondent students are in the adolescent stage. This result is supported by Manago (2019) that majority of Grade 10 students have ages from 16-17 years old.

Sex. It can be seen in the table that 256 or 71% of the respondents are male. This indicates that Grade 10 is male-dominated. This is in consonance to the study of Helmer (2020) that majority of Grade 10 students are male.

Academic Performance. Table 2 showed that 213 or 59% of the respondents have general weighted mean of 85-89. This implies that majority of the respondent students have very satisfactory grade.

Parents' Civil Status. It can be seen in the table that 321 or 89% of the respondents have married parents. This corroborates with the findings of Montenegro (2019) that majority of students in public school have students with married parents.

Monthly Family Income. It is presented in Table 2 that 181 or 50% of the respondents have monthly family income of 8,000.00-14,999.00. This denotes that half of the respondents belong to low income earner families. This is supported by the report of Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) that majority of students in public schools belong to families with low income.

Occupation of Parents. Table 2 divulged that 140 or 39% of the students have parents who are famers. This implies that majority of the students' family income rely on farming. This is because Urdaneta City is also an agricultural area; hence, farming is one of the major sources of income among families in the city.

Socio-Cultural Behaviors of Grade 10 Public Junior High School Students

Table 3 presents the extent of manifestation of socio-cultural behaviors of Grade 10 public junior high school students along family-related behaviors.

It can be gleaned in Table 3 that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.87 denoting a descriptive equivalent of "Highly Manifested" along family-related behaviors. This implies that the respondent students always respect their siblings and obey the guidance of their parents.

Among the indicators, communicating with their parents and other members of the family obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.20 denoting a descriptive equivalent of "Highly Manifested". This means that the students have open communication with their parents and other family members which is very important in a family because it leads to better understanding and respect among everyone. According to Martinez (2024), open communication helps solve disagreements more smoothly and strengthens the connection between family members, ensuring everyone feels valued and heard.

Table 3. *Family-Related Behaviors*

<i>As a student, I...</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1.	always respect and obey the guidance of my parents	4.12	Highly Manifested
2.	ask permission before doing things and going somewhere with friends	3.86	Highly Manifested
3.	use polite expressions and modulated forms of speech at all times	3.60	Highly Manifested
4.	listen to the advice of my parents	4.10	Highly Manifested
5.	assist elders and siblings in their works	4.00	Highly Manifested
6.	help in keeping cleanliness and orderliness in the house	3.20	Moderately Manifested
7.	communicate with my parents and other members of the family	4.20	Highly Manifested
8.	do not destroy and spoil things at home	3.76	Highly Manifested
9.	do not disturb my siblings when they are working	4.10	Highly Manifested
10.	always ask permission when I get things from my siblings	3.80	Highly Manifested
Overall Weighted Mean		3.87	Highly Manifested

Legend: 4.50–5.00 Very Highly Manifested (VHM); 3.50–4.49 Highly Manifested (HM); 2.50–3.49 Moderately Manifested (MM); 1.50–2.49 Slightly Manifested (SM); 1.00–1.49 Not Manifested (NM)

On the other hand, helping in keeping cleanliness and orderliness in the house obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.20 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Moderately Manifested”. This implies that the respondent students seldom help their family members in keeping the cleanliness and orderliness of the house.

This is parallel to the study of Valencia (2020) which found out that majority of students seldom help their family members in cleaning the house during pandemic.

Table 4 presents the extent of manifestation of socio-cultural behaviors of Grade 10 public junior high school students along peer-related behaviors.

Table 4. *Peer-Related Behaviors*

<i>As a student, I...</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1.	am eager to meet and greet new friends	3.60	Highly Manifested
2.	show empathy toward others	3.90	Highly Manifested
3.	do not inflict physical or moral injuries/pain on my classmates	4.20	Highly Manifested
4.	do not encourage friends and classmates to indulge in any form of gambling	4.26	Highly Manifested
5.	do not bring pornographic materials to the school	3.90	Highly Manifested
6.	encourage my friends to participate in productive activities	4.20	Highly Manifested
7.	display good self-discipline with others	4.46	Highly Manifested
8.	use decent communication with my classmates and others	4.20	Highly Manifested
9.	avoid joining any fraternities in the school	4.50	Very Highly Manifested
10.	help others do their work	4.00	Highly Manifested
Overall Weighted Mean		4.12	Highly Manifested

Legend: 4.50–5.00 Very Highly Manifested (VHM); 3.50–4.49 Highly Manifested (HM); 2.50–3.49 Moderately Manifested (MM); 1.50–2.49 Slightly Manifested (SM); 1.00–1.49 Not Manifested (NM)

It can be noted in Table 4 that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.12 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Manifested” along peer-related behaviors. This implies that the respondent students have good relationship with their peers/friends by showing empathy to others and participating in productive activities.

Among the indicators, avoiding to join in any fraternities in the school obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.50 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Very Highly Manifested”. This denotes that the respondent students do not indulge in fraternities. As mandated by the Department of Education, all schools should ensure a child-friendly environment which includes absence of fraternities or groups that may inflict harm to the learners.

Meanwhile, eagerness to meet and greet new friends obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.60 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Manifested”. This signifies that the respondent students are friendly. This corroborates the study of Anamos (2020) that youths nowadays are very eager to find new friends in school to explore adventure with them and have the feeling of belongingness.

Table 5 presents the extent of manifestation of socio-cultural behaviors of Grade 10 public junior high school students along community-related behaviors.

Table 5 which is shown in the next page revealed that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.13 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Manifested” along community-related behaviors. This signifies that the respondent students follow community rules and regulations and respect people in the community.

Among the indicators, showing respect by greeting other people in society obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.75 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Very Highly Manifested”. This implies that the respondent students possess the characteristic of being respectful by greeting other people. According to Hams (2021), greeting other people is an opportunity to demonstrate respect for others and to create a favorable impression of oneself to others.

Table 5. Community-Related Behaviors

<i>As a student, I...</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1.	obey the community rules and regulations	4.25	Highly Manifested
2.	treat all people with respect	4.00	Highly Manifested
3.	help my neighbor in maintaining cleanliness and orderliness of surroundings	3.30	Moderately Manifested
4.	always ask permission from my parent when going out	3.92	Highly Manifested
5.	show respect by greeting other people in society	4.75	Very Highly Manifested
6.	avoid arguing with my family and friends	4.25	Highly Manifested
7.	open my problems to my family	3.80	Highly Manifested
8.	respect the opinion and decision of my parents and friends	3.99	Highly Manifested
9.	always listen to my parents' advises	4.60	Very Highly Manifested
10.	always listen to my friends' advises	4.40	Highly Manifested
Overall Weighted Mean		4.13	Highly Manifested

Legend: 4.50–5.00 Very Highly Manifested (VHM); 3.50–4.49 Highly Manifested (HM); 2.50–3.49 Moderately Manifested (MM); 1.50–2.49 Slightly Manifested (SM); 1.00–1.49 Not Manifested (NM)

On the other hand, helping neighbor in maintaining cleanliness and orderliness of surroundings obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.30 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Moderately Manifested”. This denotes that the respondent students seldom collaborate with neighborhood in ensuring clean and orderly surroundings. According to Lenard (2022), teaming-up with neighbors in maintaining clean and orderly environment promotes strong bond with neighborhood and makes life healthier, less stressful, and more pleasant.

Table 6 which is shown in the next page presents the extent of manifestation of socio-cultural behaviors of Grade 10 public junior high school students along teacher-related behaviors.

Table 6. Teacher-Related Behaviors

<i>As a student, I...</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1.	obey the advice of my teachers	4.20	Highly Manifested
2.	treat my teacher as my second parent	4.00	Highly Manifested
3.	help my teacher maintain cleanliness and orderliness in the classroom	3.80	Highly Manifested
4.	always ask permission from my teacher when going out	3.90	Highly Manifested
5.	show respect by greeting my teacher	4.41	Highly Manifested
6.	avoid arguing with my teacher	4.20	Highly Manifested
7.	open my problems to my teacher	3.40	Moderately Manifested
8.	respect the opinion and decision of my teacher	3.90	Highly Manifested
9.	help my teacher in bringing or carrying things in the classroom	4.60	Very Highly Manifested
10.	always listen to my teacher when she is teaching	4.70	Very Highly Manifested
Overall Weighted Mean		4.11	Highly Manifested

Legend: 4.50–5.00 Very Highly Manifested (VHM); 3.50–4.49 Highly Manifested (HM); 2.50–3.49 Moderately Manifested (MM); 1.50–2.49 Slightly Manifested (SM); 1.00–1.49 Not Manifested (NM)

It is highlighted in Table 6 that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.11 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Manifested” along teacher-related behaviors. This implies that the respondent students have established good rapport and relationship with their teachers. Among the indicators, always listening to teachers when they are teaching obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.70 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Very Highly Manifested”. This denotes that the respondent students are attentive during class discussion. According to Montero (2022), listening to teachers during class discussion is a way of showing respect.

Meanwhile, opening problems to teacher, obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.40 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Moderately Manifested”. This means that the respondent students are hesitant in sharing their problems with their teacher. This result is parallel to the study of Vergara (2021) which revealed that majority of the students are hesitant in opening their problems with their teachers. His study also pointed out that students are more open to share their problems with their peers than their teachers.

Table 7 presents the summary table of the extent of manifestation of socio-cultural behaviors of Grade 10 public junior high school students.

Table 7. Summary Table Extent of Manifestation of Socio-Cultural Behaviors

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Overall Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Family-Related Behaviors	3.87	Highly Manifested
Peer-Related Behaviors	4.12	Highly Manifested
Community-Related Behaviors	4.13	Highly Manifested
Teacher-Related Behaviors	4.11	Highly Manifested
Grand Weighted Mean	4.06	Highly Manifested

Legend: 4.50–5.00 Very Highly Manifested (VHM); 3.50–4.49 Highly Manifested (HM); 2.50–3.49 Moderately Manifested (MM); 1.50–2.49 Slightly Manifested (SM); 1.00–1.49 Not Manifested (NM)

It can be noted in Table 7 that the respondents obtained a grand weighted mean of 4.06 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Manifested”. This implies that the respondent students strongly manifest socio-cultural behaviors. Among the indicators, community-

related behaviors obtained the highest overall weighted mean of 4.13 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Manifested” while family-related behaviors obtained the lowest overall weighted mean of “Highly Manifested”.

Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Respondents and the Extent of Manifestation their Socio-Cultural Behaviors

Table 8 on the page presents the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the extent of manifestation of their socio-cultural behaviors

Table 8. *Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Respondents and the Extent of Manifestation of their Socio-Cultural Behavior*

Profile	Extent of Manifestation of Socio-Cultural Behavior			
	Family-Related Behavior	Peer-Related Behavior	Community-Related Behavior	Teacher-Related Behavior
Age	.425	.324	.274	.357
Sex	.153	.674	.544	.224
Academic Performance	.634	.654	.633	.004*
Parents' Civil Status	.554	.641	.244	.334
Monthly Family Income	.356	.276	.432	.473
Occupation of Parents	.484	.532	.273	.533

Note: * significant at 5% alpha

It is reflected in Table 8 that there is significant relationship between the academic performance of the students and their teacher-related behaviors as indicated by the computed significance value of .004 which is less than the set level of significance which is .05. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the students and their teacher-related behaviors is rejected. The result is in consonance to the study of Miller (2019) which found out that students who perform better in class possess good teacher-related behaviors in class than those who students who are not performing well. He added that those students who perform better always listen to their teachers during class discussion. They also have strong student-teacher relationship.

Conclusions

Majority of the Grade 10 students are 16 years old, male, having a very satisfactory performance, with married parents working as farmers and low income earners.

The Grade 10 students possess strong manifestation of their socio-cultural behaviors.

Academic performance and teacher-related behaviors are correlated.

A proposed list of activities was crafted based on the salient findings of the study to enhance the socio-cultural behaviors of the students.

Teachers and students can adopt the activities crafted by the researcher to enhance the socio-cultural behavior of students.

Teachers should recognize problems encountered that may pose an effect to the socio-cultural behavior of students.

A similar study should be conducted taking into consideration other factors that can affect the socio-cultural behavior of students.

Future researchers could utilize the result of this study for their future references.

References

- Anamos, J. (2020). Influence of Socio-cultural Factors on Performance in Examinations. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 7(1), 1-14.
- Awan, Abdul Ghafoor & Ahson, Nimra (2015). Impact of Quality Management Practices on the performance of employees: A case study of selected Banks of Pakistan. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, Vol 6 .134-146.
- Awan, Abdul Ghafoor & Farhan, Hafiz Muhammad (2016). Talent Management practices and their impact on job satisfaction of employees: A case study of Banking sector in Pakistan. *Science International*, Vol 28 .
- Antil, L., Jenkins, J., & Watkins, S. (1998). Cooperative learning: Prevalence, conceptualizations, and the relation between research and practice. *American Educational Research Journal*, 35(3), 419-454.
- Bonk, C. J., & Cunningham, D. J. (1998). Searching for learner-centered, constructivist, and sociocultural components of collaborative educational learning tools. In C. J. Bonk, & K. S. King (Eds.), *Electronic collaborators: Learner-centered technologies for literacy, apprenticeship, and discourse* (pp. 25-50). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Brame, C. (2013). Flipping the classroom. Vanderbilt University Center for Teaching. Retrieved from <http://cft.vanderbilt.edu/guides-sub-pages/flipping-the-classroom>.

- Bransford, J. D., Sherwood, R. D., Hasselbring, T. S., Kinzer, C. K., & Williams, S. M. (1990). Anchored instruction: Why we need it and how technology can help. In D. Nix & R. Sprio (Eds.), *Cognition, education and multimedia* (pp. 115-141). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum Associates.
- Brill, J. M. (2001). Situated cognition. In M. Orey (Ed.), *Emerging perspectives on learning, teaching, and technology*. Retrieved November 2, 2017, from <http://epltt.coe.uga.edu/>
- Briner, M. (1999). What is constructivism? University of Colorado at Denver School of Education. Retrieved from [://curriculum.calstatela.edu/faculty/psparks/theorists/501const.htm](http://curriculum.calstatela.edu/faculty/psparks/theorists/501const.htm)
- Brown, J.S., Collins, A., Duguid, P. (1989). Situated cognition and the culture of learning. *Educational Researcher*, 18(1). pp. 32-42
- Capraro, R. M., Capraro, M. M., Morgan, J. R. (2013). *STEM project-based learning: An integrated science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) approach*. Rotterdam, The Netherlands: Sense Publishers.
- Collins, A. (1988). Cognitive apprenticeship and instructional technology. (Technical Report No. 6899). BBN Labs Inc., Cambridge.
- Chen, S.Y., & Fu, Y.C. (2009). Internet Use and Academic Achievement: Gender Differences in Early Adolescence. 44 (176).
- Duke, N. (2000). For the rich it's richer: Print environments and experiences offered to first-grade students in very low- and very high-SES school districts. *American Educational Research Journal*, 37 (2), 456.
- Educause Learning Institute. (2012). 7 things you should know about...flipped classroom. Retrieved from <https://net.educause.edu/ir/library/pdf/eli7081.pdf>
- Fogleman, J., McNeill, K. L., & Krajcik, J. (2011). Examining the effect of teachers' adaptations of a middle school science inquiry-oriented curriculum unit on student learning. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 48(2), 149-169.
- Garcia, E. (2017). A starter's guide to PBL fieldwork. Retrieved from: <https://www.edutopia.org/article/starters-guide-pbl-fieldwork>.
- Garrison, D. R., Anderson, T., & Archer, W. (2000). Critical inquiry in a text-based environment: Computer conferencing in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 2(2-3), 87-105.
- Garrison, D. R., & Akyol, Z. (2012). The community of inquiry theoretical framework. In M. G. Moore (Ed). *Handbook of Distance Education* (3rd edition), 104-120.
- Grabinger, S., Aplin, C., & Ponnappa-Brenner, G. (2007). Instructional design for sociocultural learning environments. *Journal of Instructional Science and Technology*, 10(1).
- Gonzalez, V. (2001). The role of socioeconomic and sociocultural factors in language minority children's development: An ecological research view. *Bilingual Research Journal*, 25.
- Hams, J. P. (Ed.). (2021). *Sociocultural theory and second language learning* (Vol. 78, No. 4). Oxford university press.
- Helmer, J. (2020). Impact of Socio-Cultural Factors on Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Physics, *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 7(8), 129-134.
- Lenard, M. (2022). Influence of Cultural Factors on Pupils' transition from Primary to Secondary Schools in Nakuru County, Kenya. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 6(10), 701-710.
- MA.Deal, A. (2009). A teaching with technology white paper: Collaboration tools. Retrieved from https://www.cmu.edu/teaching/technology/whitepapers/CollaborationTools_Jan09.pdf
- Manago, O. (2019). Socio-Cultural Diversity as Determinant of Social Studies Students' Academic Performance in Calabarzon. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 14(18), 688-696.
- Martinez, M. S. (2024). International student's academic achievement: Contribution of gender, self-efficacy and socio-cultural adjustment. *Asian Social Science*, 11(10), 153-158.
- Miller A. G. (2019). Impact of socio-cultural factors on academic performance of students in District Multan-Pakistan. *Global Journal of Management, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(3), 425-452.
- Montenegro, M. (2019). Bridging socio-cultural incongruity: Conceptualising the success of students from low socio-economic status backgrounds in Philippine higher education. *Studies in Higher Education*, 38(6), 939-949.
- Rogers, E. M. (2002). Diffusion of preventive innovations. *Addictive Behaviors*, 27 (6), 989-993. NIMH. 1982. Health Resource Administration. US. Department of Health and Human Services, National Institute for Medical Health, pub. (HRA) 74-1005.
- Valencia, G. (2020). *Socio-Cultural Factors Affecting Primary Education Performance In Public Primary Schools*, (Doctoral Dissertation, School Of Education).

Zhu, Nan (2020) Effects of Peer Influences and Life-History Strategy on Chinese Junior High School Students' Prosocial and Antisocial Behaviors. *Front. Educ.*, 22 October 2020. *Sec. Educational Psychology* Volume 5 - 2020
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